
Impact and Access of Consumer Behavior in Automobile Industries: A Study on Two-Wheelers Segment

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the consumers behavior' with reference to automobile industry (two wheeler) in Aligarh city Rajasthan (INDIA). The Group surveyed 100 consumers using semi-structured questionnaires to examine people perception about two wheelers and assess their behavior and willingness to pay for such products. The study revealed that all respondents are willing to pay price premium, but the level of acceptability varied considerably and some factor work behind this behavior show by the consumer. "Consumer is king" the statement carries profound truth in it. Today the success of any firm is depending upon the satisfaction of consumer. For satisfying the consumer the firm should know about the behavior of consumer. The study manly focus on understanding the factors like demographic, social cultural, price, quality, product attributes etc for buying two wheelers. A total of 58% of the consumers are willing to pay premium price of bikes. Comparatively sale of scoters are less. Mostly consumer want bikes and give preference for buying bikes that have better design, comfort, mileage, fuel efficiency etc. The survey also suggested that the consumption of two

wheelers is increasing; however, product development and innovations in certification, Processing, labeling and packaging are needed to further stimulate demand.

Introduction:

The field of consumer buying behavior studies how individuals, groups, and organizations select, buy, use, and dispose of goods, services, ideas, or experiences to satisfy their needs and desires.

Available resources (time, money efforts) on consumption related items. It include the study of what they buy, why they buy it, when they buy it, where they buy it, how often they it, and how often they use it.

In an environment where the increase in inflation, fuel prices and interest rates has been the archenemy of growth in the Indian automobile industry at large, the 2W industry has been the most tough and was reflected in its vigorous volume growth. A long-term trend of consumers preferring premium bikes should resume – volumes should recover, though timing will remain uncertain. Even though the number of offerings in the premium segment seems high, maximum volume churners still remain the products in executive & economy segments.

According to the International Yearbook of Industrial Statistics 2010 released by United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), India ranks 11th in the list of the world's top 15 automakers. Availability of easy credit for two-wheelers in rural and smaller urban areas also requires more focused attention. There is a large untapped market in semi-urban and rural areas of the country.

OBJECTIVE

The aim of this study is to shed light on consumers' behavior about two wheeler bikes and their willingness to pay for such bikes.

More specifically, the objectives of the study are:

- To increase understanding of consumers' awareness, attitude and perceptions towards two wheeler.
- To assess consumers' & retailers satisfaction level for two wheeler.
- To identify factors influencing consumers' willingness to pay (WTP) for two wheeler, and to know the most influence media to create awareness regarding two wheelers.
- To identify which particular two-wheeler have more image in the market and To know the market

share of two-wheelers

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

These ten domains of consumer satisfaction include: Quality, Value, Timeliness, Efficiency, Ease of Access, Environment, Inter-departmental Teamwork, Front line Service Behaviors, Commitment to the Customer and Innovation.

This provides the measurer with a satisfaction "gap" which is objective and quantitative in nature customer satisfaction equals perception of performance divided by expectation of performance. It may be worthwhile to explore the intricate aspects of consumer satisfaction level which focuses on 'consumer needs'.

The term consumer behavior that consumer's display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of products and services that they expect, will satisfy their needs, consumers are highly complex individuals, subjects to a variety of psychological needs apart from their survival needs. Needs and priorities of different consumer segments differ drastically. Present day consumers have wide range of transportation needs, and they take decision on how to spend their available resources such as time, money and effort on the modes and means of transport.

A large part of two wheelers are sold in the rural areas. Motorcycles, which are strong, sturdy and fuel-efficient, are better suited for the uneven and rough roads in the rural areas than any other two-wheeler.

In general, the willingness to pay a price premium decreases as the price premium increases, consistent with the law of demand. In consumer behavior theory, consumers make their own decisions to balance the marginal health utility and marginal price of one unit of quality products.

In this research, a simple framework was used to analyze consumer behavior onwards products, which includes the willingness to pay a price premium. Consumers decide whether to buy a product or not based on three main aspects: Knowledge, Attitude and Intention. Knowledge about products and their benefits influences their willingness to pay for the products. Knowledge of people is affected by type and quality of information made available to consumers. Advertisement, quality packaging, labeling and certification play pivotal role in knowledge enrichment. Once a consumer is ready to buy, the next step is to see how much he or she is willing to pay for the product.

Purchase behavior reflects the real WTP and the consumer gains positive or negative experiences which will reversely affect consumers' WTP in future. Knowledge and awareness have respectively direct and

indirect effects on attitudes toward consumer to Choose the products, and the willingness to pay a price premium, so they are important factors determining the demand. Thus, awareness and knowledge about organically produced foods are critical in the consumer willingness to pay more for the product. Similarly, the framework presented in Figure 2 reflects the factors affecting consumer's attitude and willingness to purchase. Consumer's behavior and

Willingness to purchase is affected by exogenous factors like processing, packaging, certification and labeling and consumers' knowledge and awareness about the products. If an individual cannot clearly differentiate between two alternative products, a price premium on the organic product can confuse and/or affect the individual's purchasing decision. Consumers' education, occupation, household size along with product attributes affects their attitude and preference to buy the products. These factors further depend on consumers' household income and product price to make a decision for purchase.

Figure 1: Framework reflecting consumer behavior towards food products (adopted from - Millock (2002) and Bonti-Ankomah and Yiridoe (2006))

METHODOLOGY

Respondents from the different locations from Aligarh city Is used as Sample Size. The results and responses were recorded on a SPSS data viewer (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Parameters were defined on a SPSS variable viewer.

The parameters were set up giving preference to non- demographic factors more than demographic factors. The questionnaire was developed through pre-testing of each question via

Personal interviews with the consumers. The interviewed individuals were asked to state their interpretations of a series of suggested questions. Structured (Close ended) Questionnaire is used as tool and analysis for study, a total of 100 peoples have been sampled for the purpose for the questionnaire. Details of the Survey Conducted and Target Population (20-25 years (25-30 years), (30 and above) is used in Khair, Iglas & Sasni.

The respondents were questioned on:

- Educational Institutes (University) and Petrol Pumps.
- Automobile Service Stations and Showrooms.
- Shopping Malls, Residential Areas and Factories.

The data was analyzed on the total of 12 parameters as mentioned below:

- i. Customer's Age
- ii. Marital Status
- iii. Professions
- iv. Education
- v. Marital Status
- vi. Company Prospective About Consumer
- vii. Explanation of Product Features.
- viii. Brand Preference By Consumer ,
- ix. Source of Finance.
- x. Environmental Factor Effect Purchased Bike.
- xi. Innovation
- xii. Attribute Consumer Like In Brand

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Major brand of two-wheeler marketed in Aligarh city

The diverse ranges of bikes are marketed in Aligarh city according to two wheeler showroom reported that they are currently selling about 10 different company bikes, 4 different company s scooters in Aligarh. The major bikes marketed in the city are HERO, HONDA, TVS and YAMAHA .

- Mostly the fashionable bikes like pulsar 220 DTSI, Avenger, Honda Shine, H o n d a Unicorn and YAMAHA Gla diatorhighly demanded for salad purpose.

Reported that average peoples of town are known about the present two wheeler companies are

(According to my finding out of my sample size) 62% peoples know 5 to 8 brand of bikes. Only 32% know 3-5 brands of bikes (Who belong to rural background).

In SCOOTER 75% peoples know all brands of scoter present in town and only 25% peoples know the 2-3 brands of Scoters.

Motorbikes:

Hero, Honda, Bajaj, Suzuki, TVS, Enfield, Yamaha, Thunderbird and kinetic

SCOOTER:

LML, Kinetic Engineering, Honda,hero electric, Bajaj, Yamaha

CONSUMERS' PREFERENCE ON TWO WHEELER:

We examined whether people have any preferences on two wheelers that are stylist bikes. About 60% of the respondents reported that bikes are their first choice Followed by scooters(28%) and mopeds (12%).

The main reasons given for their preferences are bikes that have better pickup, fuel efficiency and Resale value.

Finding: 60 people wants motorcycle. 28 person's wants scooter and only 12 person wants moped for their uses.

ATTRIBUTES AFFECTING CONSUMER'S WILLINGNESS TO PURCHASE:

Consumers' willingness to purchase is influenced by various. The major attributes

Identified by the consumers is lack of information available to consumers, higher prices over those of conventional bikes and the limited and erratic domestic supply. Some attributes are

- | | | |
|--------------------|-----------------------|---------------|
| (1.) Luggage space | (2.) Fuel Efficiency, | (3.) Pick up |
| (4.) Resale value | (5.) Driving comfort | (6.) Out look |

The majority of the consumers reported that 48% consumer wants all attributes in the bikes. 27% consumers want fuel efficiency, pickup and outlook, 20% consumer care about fuel efficiency, pickup and resale value. Only 4% consumer wants luggage space in the bikes.

Price is also supported by the study conducted

SOURCE OF FINANCE (PURCHASING POWER) FOR PURCHASING TWO WHEELERS:

In this 35% consumer are self-financed .he arranged money for purchasing bikes self (through fixed deposit, monthly salary, or savings etc.).

Today buyer has an advantage of finance company. Consumer purchase bikes through finance company. He takes money from finance institutes pay interest rate for purchasing bikes.

FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMERS' PERCEPTION:

Consumers' behavior is influenced by various factors. The major factors

Identified by the consumers are lacks of information available to consumers, higher prices over those of bikes, and the limited sources. The majority of the consumers reported that they are not getting regular supply of the two wheelers. This makes them frustrated to go to buy again. Besides, most of the consumer also mentioned that they do not trust the quality of two wheelers. Psychological, social, demographic factor also affected the buying behavior of consumer.

CONSUMERS' VIEWS FOR THE PROMOTION OF TWO WHEELERS:

Increased demand of bikes that willingness of the people to pay price premium for two wheeler brands models is increasing. While asking the consumers what are the key areas needed to be improved for the promotion of this sector, the answer from majority of them was that quality is the number one priority area which needs to be improved to increase the demand for bikes. The quality of the present products is not satisfactory though consumers are using such bikes mainly due to the fashion status reasons.

Similarly, the consumers reported that there is urgent need to work on processing, packaging and labeling to inform the consumers. At present, consumers are buying the two wheelers based on their trust with the traders and manufacturer. In such cases, consumers have put forward their opinion for the certification of the bikes with authorized certification. That can help differentiate the one company bikes from other bikes company, which can be helpful to promote Organically grown two wheeler markets.

The survey revealed that many people are not well aware about the availability of the different- different models of bikes in the market. Those who are aware about this and buying from one store are also not well aware about other outlets where they can buy the bikes. It is therefore, necessary to disseminate and publicize the information widely so that all the people can have access to information and can make their own decision.

40% of the surveyed consumers reported that the get information about product through print media. 20%by trade show, 20% from brand image word of mouth15%by electronic media and 5% through exhibition.

Figure 2: external factor influence print media 40%, e media 15%, exhibition 5%, trade show 20%, Brand image 20% people

PRESENTLY BRAND (BIKES) USING BY THE CONSUMERS:

Presently out of 100 respondent 40% used Hero Honda bikes, 20% have Bajaj bikes like discover, patina, avenger and 15% purchased TVS bikes(TVS star, TVS pep, apache) and 16% Yamaha bikes (gladiator, alba, etc.), 4% have Honda bike like Honda shine .

Finding 3: **PRESENTLY BRAND (BIKES) USING BY THE CONSUMER**

PREFERANCE GIVEN BY COMPANY FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT:

The 85% Respondent consumer want new innovation in bike. Better technology, features and usp in bikes for show the status symbol of life. Only 15% who have latter adopter and up to 35 age consumer don't want any innovation in bikes. Many consumers want some unique properties in bike like Acceptability of customer, Scale of economic, Comfort, Design etc.

Finding: PREFERANCE GIVEN BY COMPANY FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

MARKET COVERED BY TWO WHEELER COMPANY:

- 40% market covered by Bajaj company major models Bajaj Avenger, Bajaj Discover, Bajaj Patina, Pulsar 180 DTS-i UG, Pulsar 150 DTS-i UG, Pulsar 200 Cc Pulsar 220 DTS-Fi, Purchased by consumers. for the resign of new design and innovation in technology, mileage, pickup etc. 20%

consumer have TVs bikes like star ,star city, for the region of comparatively low price and milage.20% consumer have Yamaha bike because of new style , speed and new models. Consumer of hero Honda sparred in two groups as hero Moto corp. and Honda bikes.

Finding: MARKET COVERED BY TWO WHEELER COMPANY

DISCUSSION

1. Out of the six brands covered the respondents of Suzuki are generally married while other brands have unmarried customers
2. The average age of a Yamaha customer comes out to be 26-30 years as compared to others brands average customers age which is 21-25 years.
3. When explanation of product features comes into view; only Yamaha customers rank them average; others says it's good.
4. Hero Honda and Honda are most favored brands when timely delivery of bike comes into picture
5. Suzuki customers says that they have to run after their dealers for the documentation of the delivery done while others say they are satisfied.
6. Hero Honda is best when sales follow up after delivery is concerned .before separation of Hero Moto corp. Honda.
7. The most important point that comes up after analysis is that almost every brand of customer wants a

change but customers are generally loyal to their brand like hero Honda and Yamaha. To conclude it can be said that almost every brand lacks in terms of sales follow up. So this is the area where bike ind. can focus and position its bikes.

Secondly, there is huge market for bikes because almost every bike user wants to change its bike because of some or the other reason. Lastly, Yamaha, bajaj, Hero Honda have a good market

Images but a minimum number of users are new. The most raring point is that Yamaha, TVs, hero, Honda, in spite of having a low market share is able to retain most of its customers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

There are various conclusions that can be arrived at regarding the Indian two wheeler industry after the execution of this research. Still the research cannot be considered as totally exhaustive. There are various areas that are beyond the scope of this research. This arises the need and scope of further research in this area. Some of the possible arenas can be as follows:

- Forecasting the market for two wheeler industry in coming 5 years and • Study of consumer behavior towards Indian two wheeler industries
- Developing a model for success of a particular brand on the basis of arrived conclusions. • and Developing a model of bike on the basis of responses of the customers to stabilize in the market; determining the optimum combination of mileage and price.
- Yamaha has no vulnerable bike to compete with high mileage bikes of TVS, Hero Honda and Honda.
- Yamaha bikes have a poor mileage it needs to create a positive image in the mind of its customers. • They lack style and innovation. • Yamaha has no raring 150 cc range bike. • Yamaha , Hero , Honda lacks in aggressive marketing strategy.
- Indian customers are mainly commuters and not bikers. • People having a halo image of RX-100. •• Dearer accessories & High maintenance cost in premium bike.
- Hero Honda has lost trust after separation hero and Honda among Indian consumers by producing bikes like splendor, passion and passion+ .
- Customers stress on quality as complimentary to looks. • Mileage is what everybody wants.
- Age group – 21-35 years • Profession – Mostly salaried

- Customers are generally satisfied with attitude of dealers at the time of sales.
- Every brand of bikes has a poor response in terms of sales follow up.
- Hero Honda is the most famous brand. • Favored bikes in today's date are – Bajaj pulsar DTSI 135 CC, 220 CC bike and Bajaj discover & avenger.

Suggestion

- INTRODUCTION OF NEW BRANDS: Yamaha, Honda, hero Moto corp. should introduce new bikes in the market. It will definitely make the market oligopolistic, but will improve the condition of Yamaha.
- BIKE IN 150 CC SEGMENT – Yamaha, TVS, Suzuki, does not have any successful bike in these segments. Yamaha needs to introduce a bike in this segment which can compete with the other brands on price, power, pick-up, mileage and style.
- INTEGRATION OF MARKETING AND R & D DEPARTMENT - Yamaha has got best R&D facilities and international design of sports bikes. It needs to integrate its efforts together with other department more specifically marketing wing and try to give customers what they want.
- It has been found from the research that Yamaha, Honda, Bajaj has got the most loyal customers but when it comes to Yamaha, people still talk about RX- 100. Yamaha should develop a bike like RX- 100, and this time mileage and style should also be considered.
- 360 degree marketing approach and need to follow aggressive promotional campaigns to grab a larger piece of pie in the motorcycle segment.
- Focus should be on teenagers, young and executives as they represent largest portion of the bike user segment.
- Provide better sales follow up which almost every brand lacks – the research has showed that the bike users of all brands are dissatisfied with their 'after sales experience' .this is a big loop hole which Yamaha can use to improve its brand image and to gain more customers.
- Indian customers generally do not use bike for fashion but as a necessity so mileage should be a concern, so it needs to create a better image in the mind of its customers regarding mileage.
- Sometimes it was very difficult to get the necessary information as filling the questionnaire required

time. Research could have been wider in scope if along with customer satisfaction level consumer behavior pattern was also studied.

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